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“Calculating the change in Gibbs free energy (ddGbind) of inhibitor binding associated with genetic variations of SARS-CoV-2 Main Protease”

Step 1: Genetic diversity at the catalytic site of the SARS-CoV-2 main protease (MPro).

I sent the list of 21 residues forming the SARS-CoV-2 MPro catalytic site to our collaborator on this project, Nicola di Maio, in Nick Goldman's lab at EBI. Nicola used his last batch of over 15000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples (as of May 17th, 2020) to identify all mutations at these 21 positions. Nicola reported his findings in his recent post on OpenLabNotebook¹ alongside his methods on Zenodo.² Nicola identified a few, rare mutations at the MPro catalytic site across more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples: M49I, P52S, N142S, and P168S. In Table 1, details about each of the 21 positions are shown.

Number	Residues	Gene Locus		
		Codon 1	Codon 2	Codon 3
1	T25 'T': 15864	'a': 15874	'c': 15874	't': 15862, 'c': 2 Note: here the 2 c's at third codon position do not seem reliable, but they are synonymous anyway
2	Leu27 'L': 15874	'c': 15874	't': 15874	't': 15873, 'c': 1
3	His41 'H': 15812			
4	Cys44 'C': 15813	't': 15813	'g': 15814	'c': 15812, 't': 2
5	Met49 'M': 15809, 'I': 1 sample with "I" variant from Scotland, EPI_ISL_425839 2020-03-13	'a': 15812	't': 15810	'g': 15809, 't': 1

6	Pro52 'P': 15808, 'S': 2 samples with "S" variants from Russia, EPI_ISL_428864 2020- 03-11 and EPI_ISL_428863 2020- 03-11	'c': 15808, 't': 2	'c': 15810	't': 15812
7	Tyr54 {'Y': 15815}			
8	Phe140 'F': 15874			
9	Asn142 'N': 15871, 'S': 1 sample with "S" variant from USA, EPI_ISL_427164 2020- 03-31	'a': 15872	'a': 15871, 'g': 1	't': 15870, 'c': 4
10	Ser144 'S': 15874			
11	Cys145 'C': 15874			
12	His163 'H': 15874			
13	His164 'H': 15874			
14	Met165 'M': 15874			
15	Glu166 'E': 15874			
16	Leu167 'L': 15874			

17	Pro168 'P': 15874, 'S': 1 sample with "S" variant from USA/NY, EPI_ISL_428789 2020- 04-06	'c': 15874, 't': 1	'c': 15875	'a': 15875
18	His172 'H': 15875			
19	Asp187 'D': 15872	'g': 15875	'a': 15875	'c': 15869, 't': 3
20	Gln189 'Q': 15874			
21	Gln192 'Q': 15875	'c': 15875	'a': 15875	'a': 15874, 'g': 1

Table 1. Genetic diversity at the catalytic site of the SARS-CoV-2 MPro. Each row shows an amino-acid lining the catalytic site and indicates the number of SARS-CoV-2 samples with a given sidechain at this position. Non-synonymous mutations were only found at positions highlighted in blue.

Step 2: Running energy calculation to predict computationally the effect of these mutations on ligand binding with the SARS-CoV-2 MPro.

To predict the effect of these four mutations (M49I, P52S, N142S, and P168S) on the binding of a known MPro inhibitor (PDB code 7bqy), we estimated the difference in binding energy of the ligand between the wild type and the mutated forms of the protein with ICM (Molsoft, San Diego). You can refer to ICM's tutorial for more details.³

ICM calculates the binding energy change (dG_{bind} in kcal/mol) of the ligand as the energy of the protein-ligand complex minus the energy of the isolated protein and ligand. The difference in binding energy (ddG_{bind}), which is what we are interested in, is dG_{bind} [mutant] minus dG_{bind} [wild-type]. The equation below summarizes this energy calculation.³

$$\Delta\Delta G_{bind} = \Delta G_{bind}^{mut} - \Delta G_{bind}^{wt}, \text{ where}$$

$$\Delta G_{bind} = (E_{intra}^{comp} - E_{intra}^{parts}) + (\Delta G_{solv}^{comp} - \Delta G_{solv}^{parts})$$

Since the precision of this method is about 2.0 kcal/mol, ddG_{bind} values > 2.0 kcal/mol indicate mutations that significantly penalize ligand binding.⁴ Figure 1, 2, 3, and 4 each show the energy calculation of these four mutations affecting the binding of a known inhibitor to the SARS-CoV-2 MPro (PDB code 7bqy) alongside a ribbon diagram that displays the mutated sidechain at the SARS-CoV-2 MPro catalytic site.

1. M49I

Protein	Chain	Residue	Wild type	Mutant	ddGbind	dGbind_wild	dGbind_mut
7bqy	a	49	Met	Ile	1.1	-37.08	-36

Figure 1. Energy calculation to predict computationally the effect of M49I on the binding of a known inhibitor (PDB code 7bqy) with the SARS-CoV-2 MPro.

2. P52S

Protein	chain	residue	Wild type	Mutant	ddGbind	dGbind_wild	dGbind_mut
7bqy	a	52	Pro	Ser	-0.1	-37.08	-37.17

Figure 2. Energy calculation to predict computationally the effect of P52S on the binding of a known inhibitor (PDB code 7bqy) with the SARS-CoV-2 MPro.

3.N142S

Protein	chain	residue	Wild type	Mutant	ddGbind	dGbind_wild	dGbind_mut
7bqy	a	142	Asn	Ser	0.4	-37.08	-36.66

Figure 3. Energy calculation to predict computationally the effect of N142S on the binding of a known inhibitor (PDB code 7bqy) with the SARS-CoV-2 MPro.

4. P168S

Protein	chain	residue	Wild type	Mutant	ddGbind	dGbind_wild	dGbind_mut
7bqy	a	168	Pro	Ser	1.9	-37.08	-35.21

Figure 4. Energy calculation to predict computationally the effect of P168S on the binding of a known inhibitor (PDB code 7bqy) with the SARS-CoV-2 MPro.

Step 3: Adding two positive controls to our energy calculations: Methionine 165 (M165) and glutamine 189 (Q189).

M165 and Q189 are both at positions that are critical for ligand binding. Therefore, we speculated that the ddGbind values should reflect that. To mimic M49I, we also mutated M165 to Ile, similarly we mutated Q189 to Ser to mimic N142S. Below, I show the ribbon diagrams for Control 1 and Control 2 to display the mutations, and the table above each diagram summarizes the ddGbind values for these positive controls.

Control 1: M165I. M165 lies at the bottom of the binding site where mutations are more likely to induce steric clashes.

Mutations	Residue Number	Wild Type Residue	Mutated Residue	ddGbind (kcal/mol)	dGbind wild type	dGbind mutant
control 1	165	Met	Ile	14.6	-37.1	-22.4

Figure 5. Energy calculation to predict computationally the effect of the first control mutation, M165I, on the binding of a known inhibitor (PDB code 7bqy) with the SARS-CoV-2 MPro.

Control 2: Q189S. Disruption of H-bond between N3 inhibitor (PDB code 7bqy) and MPro due to mutating Q189 to serine.

Mutations	Residue Number	Wild Type Residue	Mutated Residue	ddGbind (kcal/mol)	dGbind wild type	dGbind mutant
control 2	189	Gln	Ser	4.1	-37.1	-33.0

Figure 6. Energy calculation to predict computationally the effect of the second control mutation, Q189S, on the binding of a known inhibitor (PDB code 7bqy) with the MPro of SARS-CoV-2.

Results:

Figure 7 shows all the four mutations and the two controls. Table 2 shows that the $\Delta\Delta G_{\text{bind}}$ values for the four mutations (M49I, P52S, N142S, and P168S) range between $-0.1 < \Delta\Delta G_{\text{bind}} \text{ (kcal/mol)} < 2$. The two positive control mutations, M165I and Q189S increased the Gibbs free energy by 14.65 kcal/mol and 4.05 kcal/mol, respectively.

Figure 7. The 3D representation of SARS-CoV-2 MPro catalytic site with the inhibitor N3 (pdb code: 7bqy) and the amino acid variants at this site. The residues highlighted in light grey are positive controls (M165I, Q189S), and those in orange are the four mutations (M49I, P52S, N142S, and P168S) identified from SARS-CoV-2 genome samples from COVID-19 patient isolates. The dashed line shows the hydrogen bond between the inhibitor and Q189.

Mutations	Residue Number	Wild Type Residue	Mutated Residue	ddGbind (kcal/mol)	dGbind wild type	dGbind mutant
1	49	Met	Ile	1.1	-37.1	-36.0
2	52	Pro	Ser	-0.1	-37.1	-37.2
3	142	Asn	Ser	0.4	-37.1	-36.7
4	168	Pro	Ser	1.9	-37.1	-35.2
control 1	165	Met	Ile	14.6	-37.1	-22.4
control 2	189	Gln	Ser	4.1	-37.1	-33.0

Table 2. The energy calculation associated with the four mutations (M49I, P52S, N142S, and P168S) found in the genetic variability analysis at the catalytic site of the MPro of SARS-CoV-2. The positive control mutations are highlighted in light grey.

As you can see, for example, the positive control mutation, mutating M165 to an isoleucine residue, will increase the Gibbs binding free energy by 14.6 kCal/mol, which is very significant, while the change in Gibbs binding free energy for mutations that Nicola found in the 15000 SARS-CoV-2 samples are in the range of -0.1 kcal/mol to 2.0 kcal/mol, which is not significant (as explained above).

Consequently, our data suggest that the MPro mutations from SARS-CoV-2 samples are expected to have limited effect on the binding of inhibitor N3 with the MPro. On the other end, the two positive controls are predicted to significantly penalize ligand binding. Importantly, these are predictions only, and would need to be validated experimentally.

The limited effect of these mutations on ligand binding predicted by ICM is further supported by the fact that all these positions are at the rim of the binding site rather than deep into the pocket as shown in Figure 7. This is in contrast with the positive control M165, which lies at the bottom of the binding site: mutations are more likely to induce steric clashes. Q189, the other positive control, is also at the rim, but makes a hydrogen bond with the inhibitor, which is lost when mutated to Ser.

In conclusion, mutations identified over 15,000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples and positioned at the catalytic site of the viral MPro are rare and expected to have minimal impact on binding of N3, an inhibitor that was crystallized with the protein.

Step 4: Predicting the effect of all possible mutations at the MPro catalytic site on ligand (inhibitor N3)-binding with the SARS-CoV-2 MPro.

We created an energy matrix table where we consider the effect of every possible mutation on the binding of ligand (inhibitor N3) with CoV-2-MPro. Table 3 includes a list of the 20 residues at MPro catalytic site except Cys145. Cys145 is not included as it makes a covalent interaction with inhibitor N3: any mutation will severely affect ligand binding.

It is likely that the residues of the rows with green color are not making optimal interactions with N3. This is reflected in the very slight and non-significant lowering in ddGbind values of these residues (mutations are stabilizing) and hence the green color. On the other hand, the sidechains whose mutations are shown in orange are likely the positions where MPro would better interact with N3 which

include H41, S144, M165, E166, P168, Q189. As a result, the mutations of those sidechains are predicted to penalize inhibitor-binding significantly and hence the orange color.

Residue	Residue Number	WT	Mutant Residue																			
			gly	ala	val	leu	ile	pro	cys	met	ser	thr	phe	tyr	trp	asn	gln	asp	glu	his	lys	arg
a_7bey.ai/T25	25	T	0.7	0.8	0.3	0.3	0.4	58.7	0.6	1.0	0.9	0.0	0.7	1.0	-1.2	1.1	0.7	1.8	2.3	1.7	0.4	0.1
a_7bey.ai/L27	27	L	0.4	0.1	-0.9	0.0	-2.3	223.9	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.0	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.4	4.4	2.5	0.5	-1.9	-0.7
a_7bey.ai/H41	41	H	2.8	2.1	4.1	7.8	7.3	1.6	2.3	21.5	3.0	3.6	-1.9	-5.3	-4.4	3.1	16.0	9.1	16.9	0.0	24.3	28.5
a_7bey.ai/C44	44	C	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	-0.8	-1.0	55.9	0.0	0.5	0.1	-0.1	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.5	0.4	3.0	3.5	-0.2	-0.1	-1.5
a_7bey.ai/M49	49	M	1.9	1.4	2.0	1.0	1.1	1.4	1.3	0.0	2.2	2.5	1.9	1.2	12.4	1.3	0.7	0.8	0.6	3.0	2.0	4.5
a_7bey.ai/P52	52	P	-0.3	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.8	-0.1	0.0	-0.3	-0.3	0.0	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	1.1	0.5	-0.1	-0.1
a_7bey.ai/Y54	54	Y	-0.8	-0.8	-0.6	-0.1	-0.5	-0.9	-0.6	-0.5	-0.6	-0.6	0.3	0.0	0.4	-0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.8	0.1	-0.1	1.1
a_7bey.ai/F140	140	F	1.3	0.0	-1.2	-0.4	-1.2	47.0	-0.7	-0.2	-1.0	-2.0	0.0	-0.1	0.3	-0.1	-8.1	3.6	8.5	-0.3	-3.5	-2.3
a_7bey.ai/N142	142	N	1.0	0.4	-2.0	-0.2	-3.6	-0.1	-0.5	-0.9	0.4	-0.9	0.0	-0.4	0.9	0.0	-1.2	-0.1	-1.3	-0.2	-1.1	-0.9
a_7bey.ai/S144	144	S	-0.2	-0.4	-0.4	-0.5	-0.4	-1.2	-0.4	-1.6	0.0	-0.4	20.2	33.9	64.8	-0.2	90.9	12.6	6.7	8.0	-8.6	0.4
a_7bey.ai/H163	163	H	-2.6	-2.5	-1.5	-2.3	-1.5	-2.6	-1.4	-1.0	-1.1	-1.7	-2.0	5.9	9.3	-1.7	0.0	6.3	7.8	-7.9	-7.3	-12.0
a_7bey.ai/H164	164	H	-1.2	-1.8	-2.0	-0.9	-1.6	46.8	-1.8	-1.5	-1.8	-2.2	-0.2	0.1	0.0	-1.0	-1.1	2.3	1.7	-0.1	-1.3	-1.6
a_7bey.ai/M165	165	M	4.1	1.6	8.4	0.7	14.6	170.3	2.3	0.0	2.5	10.5	1.0	1.1	0.9	2.4	1.4	8.4	7.0	1.0	0.5	-0.1
a_7bey.ai/E166	166	E	2.8	1.7	11.8	0.4	24.0	30.7	1.7	1.3	1.8	12.7	0.4	0.4	-0.8	1.4	1.9	2.6	0.0	1.1	0.4	-0.2
a_7bey.ai/L167	167	L	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.3	-0.8	0.3	0.8	3.3	0.8	-0.1	0.2	0.0
a_7bey.ai/P168	168	P	2.3	2.1	1.5	3.0	2.1	0.0	3.5	2.0	1.9	2.4	12.5	90.8	17.1	0.6	3.0	5.9	5.4	5.6	2.7	5.4
a_7bey.ai/H172	172	H	0.3	1.2	0.8	0.5	0.8	49.3	0.7	1.0	0.7	1.0	0.1	-0.5	21.7	-1.1	0.5	5.0	3.9	0.0	-0.9	-0.9
a_7bey.ai/D187	187	D	0.3	-0.9	0.6	-0.8	0.0	62.9	-0.7	-0.9	-0.6	0.4	-0.3	-0.4	-0.7	-0.7	-1.3	0.0	0.9	-0.6	-2.2	-1.1
a_7bey.ai/Q189	189	Q	2.9	3.0	3.0	7.7	2.7	2.9	2.7	1.1	4.0	4.8	40.7	28.2	83.2	1.8	0.0	3.9	-0.3	14.3	3.6	4.3
a_7bey.ai/Q192	192	Q	1.5	0.5	0.8	0.4	0.2	-0.7	1.3	4.1	1.1	0.9	0.1	0.0	0.2	1.0	0.0	1.9	2.3	0.1	-0.4	-0.2

Table 3. The energy matrix showing the effect of all possible mutations at SARS-COV-2MPro catalytic site and the predicted effect on ligand binding. No mutations at Cys145 were considered since it makes the covalent thioether linkage with the ligand which is essential for the inhibitory mechanism in this scenario. The energy unit is kcal/mol.

Table 3 color-coding based on ddGbind value (X) in Kcal/mol
X > 10.0
4.0 > X > 10.0
2.0 > X > 4.0
-2.0 > X > 2.0
-4.0 > X > -2.0
-10.0 > X > -4.0
-10.0 > X

References:

1. Nicola De Maio. *Genetic diversity at the catalytic site of the main SARS-Cov-2 protease.* (2020) openlabnotebooks.org –<https://openlabnotebooks.org/genetic-diversity-at-the-catalytic-site-of-the-main-sars-cov-2-protease/>
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